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Data management plan (DMP)

DMP: home field advantage in professional soccer

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	27/11/2025	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

Level of distribution		This DMP is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0). It is publicly available under 10.5281/zenodo.17740846
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Project details

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	research_question_answers	Plain text	text/plain	100 - 1000 MB	no
P2	process_research_questions	Source code	application/x-python-code	100 - 1000 MB	no

Description for "research_question_answers":

This dataset is considered to be part of the produced data. It is a single text file produced as the output of a source-code execution and contains the answers to all the research questions: 1. The average points achieved from the examined teams in the examined season, separated into the home points average and the away points average. Furthermore the difference home points average minus away points average. 2. The differences home points average minus away points separated into all examined leagues in a list, furthermore the maximum and minimum value of that list. 3. Separated into the examined periods, the differences home points average minus away points average, and the change between these values.

Description for "process_research_questions":

This dataset is considered to be part of the produced data. It is a single source-code file authored by the researcher and is responsible for the accumulation and the processing transforming the reused data into the produced data using the csv library of the python programming language.

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Major football league results 2024/25	https://github.com/datasets/football-datasets	PDDL v1.0	no
R2	International football game results	https://github.com/martj42/international_results	CC0 v1.0 Universal	no

Description for "Major football league results 2024/25":

This dataset consist of five csv files, one for each examined league (Bundesliga, Premier League, Serie A, La Liga, Ligue 1). Each of these files contains the entire amount of encounters during the season with all necessary columns to answer the research questions. Each file is named "season-2425.csv", placed as the only file in a directory named after the corresponding league. The files are obtained

from the source below under the Public Domain Dedication and License v1.0

Description for "International football game results":

This dataset consist of a single csv file. It contains a selection of national-team-encounters starting with the year 1872 until 2024, with all necessary columns to answer the research questions. The file is named "results.csv" and is obtained from the source below under the Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal license

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The reused data will be accumulated and processed into the produced data using the csv library of the python programming language.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

- The project is version-controlled using Git.
- Folder structure keeps produced and reused data strictly separated:
 - /process_research_questions.py
 - /produced_data/ → contains only P1
 - /reused_data/league/<league_name>/season-2425.csv → R1
 - /reused_data/international/results.csv → R2
- Metadata:
 - README files (Markdown) describe data structure and workflow.
 - Repository-provided metadata (e.g., Dublin Core / DataCite) will be completed during publication.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: repeated samples or measurements and peer review of data.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Nikolas Graf (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will be stored on the servers of TU Wien.

P1 (research_question_answers), P2 (process_research_questions), R1 (Major football league results 2024/25), R2 (International football game results) will be stored on TUcloud: TUcloud is a sync&share service provided by Campus IT for TU Wien members. It runs on Campus IT servers and offers features known from public cloud systems, such as Dropbox, for example, the exchange of data with authorised persons. Deleted files can be recovered within 180 days.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	reading only	reading only	reading only
P2	writing	reading only	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and rights of use

- Reused datasets:
 - R1 under PDDL 1.0 → can be reused without restrictions
 - R2 under CC0 1.0 → can be reused without restrictions
- Produced datasets:
 - Licensed under **CC BY 4.0**, as declared at the top of the DMP.
- The researcher holds authorship of P1 and P2 but provides open access under CC BY.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open Access	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data	10.70124/4n9sz-sxq92	CC BY 4.0
P2	Open Access	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data	10.70124/t26cz-x7762	CC BY 4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://test.researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: There aren't any tools necessary in order to view the results of the analysis, however if one aims for running the analysis locally, a python executable is needed in order to run the script.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Anyone who's interested in the statistical analysis of professional soccer games lying in the past, including professionals working in the sports industry as well as researchers examining different research questions.
P2	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The researcher will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.